

The Rights and Duties of Members of the UWC Astronomy Group

The members of the UWC Astronomy Group are largely funded by public funds and so have the responsibility to create a research environment which is healthy, productive and safe. This document outlines the rights and duties of *all* members of the Astronomy Group, including students, postdocs, staff and administrative staff (Code of Conduct only).

Code of Conduct

The UWC Astronomy Group is committed to creating a work environment that is productive and enjoyable for everyone, regardless of gender, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, body size, race, nationality or religion. We will not tolerate harassment of group members in any form.

Please follow these guidelines:

- Behave professionally. Harassment and sexist, racist, or exclusionary comments or jokes are not appropriate. Harassment includes sustained disruption of talks or other events, inappropriate physical contact, sexual attention or innuendo, deliberate intimidation, stalking, and photography or recording of an individual without consent. It also includes offensive comments related to gender, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, body size, race or religion.
- All communication should be appropriate for a professional audience including people of many different backgrounds. Sexual language and imagery is not appropriate.
- Be kind to others. Do not insult or put down other members of the group. Any instances of bullying will not be tolerated.
- Group members asked to stop any inappropriate behaviour are expected to comply immediately. Members violating these rules may ultimately be referred to University disciplinary procedures.

Any participant who wishes to report a violation of this policy is asked to speak, in confidence, to any faculty member of the Astronomy Group.

This code of conduct is based on the "London Code of Conduct", as originally designed for the conference "Accurate Astrophysics. Correct Cosmology", held in London in July 2015. The London Code of Conduct was adapted with permission by Andrew Pontzen and Hiranya Peiris from a document by Software Carpentry (<http://software-carpentry.org/conduct.html>), which itself derives from original Creative Commons documents by PyCon and Geek Feminism. It is released under a CC-Zero licence for reuse. To help track people's improvements and best practice, please retain this acknowledgement, and log your re-use or modification of this policy at https://github.com/apontzen/london_cc.

Participation in Group Activities

- All members of the group are expected to spend the majority of the work day on campus on Mondays, Wednesdays and Fridays in order to facilitate group interaction and a thriving research environment.
- Students and postdocs must attend all journal clubs, research meetings and seminars unless granted explicit exemption from their supervisor. Staff will commit to attending these meetings as much as their travel and teaching schedules allow.
- Supervisors are responsible for ensuring their students are participating actively in group activities.
- All members of the group are expected to contribute in some way to the smooth running of the group. This can include: helping run journal club, research meetings and seminars, contributing to the professional development programme, actively engaging in outreach activities and teaching short courses or seminars to postgraduate students in the group.
- Students and postdocs will elect representatives to create a communication channel between them and the faculty for any suggestions, especially with regards to improving conditions of their workplace.

Responsible Use of Funding

Equipment and travel grants, student bursaries and postdoc salaries are generally drawn from public funds and so must be spent responsibly.

Equipment

- Equipment should only be requested that is necessary for work.
- Reasonable steps must be taken to ensure equipment is kept safe, such as not leaving laptops or other valuables in view in a car and ensuring equipment is kept in a locked office when not being used.

Travel

- Travel should only be requested if it will benefit the group member's research.
- Travel grants are finite and all group members should endeavour to make the best use of them possible to further their work and their career.

Bursaries and salaries

- Student bursaries and postdoc salaries are generally deemed sufficient for typical living expenses in Cape Town.
- Transport to campus three days a week should be considered a normal work-related expense and budgeted for. A lack of funding is not generally seen as a good reason for not coming to campus.